

Electrodeposition of Copper-Nickel Alloy from Citrate Electrolytes in Presence of Ammonium Hydroxide

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The electrodeposition of Cu-Ni alloy from citrate electrolytes in the presence of ammonium hydroxide was investigated. The effect of citric acid concentration, ammonium hydroxide concentration, metal ion concentration, current density and temperature on the quality of the deposit, the current efficiency and the alloy composition was studied. Boric acid was added to the electrolytes as buffering agent to prevent the formation of pittings. The current efficiency was found to be very high. The effect of current density and ammonium hydroxide on the composition of the alloy was explained by the polarization curves.

THE electrolytic Cu-Ni alloys are of great industrial value¹. The most widely used electrolytes for Cu-Ni alloys are the pyrophosphates²⁻⁵. These electrolytes have good throwing power and current efficiency.

The citrate electrolytes were suggested for the first time by Priscott⁶. Further development of these electrolytes was carried out by Korovin and coworkers⁷. They found that Cu-Ni deposits of good quality can be deposited only in the presence of certain organic additions. One of these additions was saccharine in amounts of 0.5 g/l. In the absence of organic additions, the deposited alloy is of low quality and cannot be deposited with considerable thicknesses. The citrate electrolyte recommended contains NiSO₄, CuSO₄, sodium citrate and sodium chloride with pH about 5.0.

In the present work we studied the conditions of the electrodeposition of Cu-Ni alloy from citrate electrolyte containing citric acid and ammonium hydroxide as complexing agents. Actually the deposition of Cu-Ni alloy was carried out from mixed citrate and ammonium complexes. It is well known that deposition potentials of copper and nickel are too far from each other to codeposit them. The use of ammonium hydroxide and citric acid makes the deposition potentials of copper and nickel closer to each other and hence makes codeposition possible⁷.

The electrolytic Cu-Ni alloys are known to form a series of continuous solid solutions⁸.

Experimental

The effect of the different factors on the quality of the deposit, its composition and current efficiency was studied in the electrolytes :

- contains 0.8*N* NiSO₄; 0.2*N* CuSO₄; 2.0*N* citric acid.
- contains 0.8*N* NiSO₄; 0.2*N* CuSO₄; 2.0*N* citric acid; 1.0*N* NH₄OH.

The temperature was adjusted to 30° ± 0.2° by means of an ultrathermostat. The plating process took 45 min at 0.5 a/dm². An alkaline battery (6 volts) was used as a source of the direct current needed for electrodeposition. A copper coulombmeter was used for evaluating the quantity of electricity passed. The evolved hydrogen on the cathode was collected to determine the current efficiency of the cathodic deposition. As reference half cell, the saturated calomel electrode was used. The deposited alloy was analyzed for copper by iodometric titration. The nickel content was determined gravimetrically by the dimethylglyoximate method. It was found that the determination of copper metal in the alloy is enough, as always the difference between the weight of the alloy and the copper was very close to that of nickel. The maximum error was found to be less than 2.0% relative to nickel. As a cathode a platinum sheet of 28.5 cm² surface area was used. Anodes were made of copper.

Results and Discussion

The effect of citric acid concentration :

The copper content in the deposited alloy increases with increasing the citric acid concentration in the

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absence of NH_4OH (electrolyte a). At concentrations of citric acid higher than $2.0N$, copper content, decreases gradually after passing through a maximum (Fig. 1). In the presence of NH_4OH (electrolyte b), the nickel content increases with increasing the citric acid concentration. At concentrations of citric acid higher than $2.0N$, the change in the alloy composition becomes very small.

Fig. 1

The increase in copper content on increasing the citric acid concentration in electrolyte (a) is due to the relative change in the stability of copper and nickel complexes with citrate ions. It is obvious that the discharge of Cu^{2+} becomes easier than Ni^{2+} when the citric acid concentration increases. At concentrations of citric acid higher than $2.0N$ Ni^{2+} discharge becomes relatively easier than Cu^{2+} discharge.

In electrolyte (b), where Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} are in the form of complexes with ammonia and citrate ions, the increasing of citric acid concentration seems to make both of these complexes less stable and easier to discharge. As citric acid concentration increases, the copper content in the alloy decreases. This is attributed to the relatively higher effect of citric acid on the stability of Ni^{2+} complexes than Cu^{2+} complexes. Moreover, it is known that the citrate complexes with Cu^{2+} are highly stable in alkaline medium⁸. Due to this fact the deposition potentials of copper shift towards more negative values, i.e., towards nickel deposition potentials.

The effect of ammonium hydroxide concentration :

The addition of $2.0N$ ammonium hydroxide to the electrolyte (a) decreases the copper content from 95% to 67% (Fig. 2), i.e., Ni^{2+} discharge becomes relatively easier than Cu^{2+} discharge. At concentrations of ammonium hydroxide higher than $2.0N$, copper content in the alloy starts to increase after going through a minimum. The appearance of the minimum corresponds to the point at which the

relative stability of Ni^{2+} complexes starts to overcome that of Cu^{2+} , i.e., the point at which the discharge of Ni^{2+} ions begins to be more difficult than the discharge of Cu^{2+} ions. As was mentioned above, the stability of Cu^{2+} complexes with citrate

Fig. 2

ions becomes very high in alkaline medium, which makes the deposition potentials of copper closer to those of nickel (Fig. 3). On these polarization curves it is clear that higher the ammonium hydroxide concentration, the lower the limiting current of copper, i.e., the higher nickel content in the alloy.

Fig. 3

The effect of metal ion concentration :

Keeping the summation of the metal concentration in solution constant, the ratio was changed from $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Ni}^{2+} = 0.2 : 0.8$ to $0.8 : 0.2$. The copper content in the alloy increases by increasing this ratio.

In electrolyte (a), the copper content increased from 95 to 100% at $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Ni}^{2+} = 0.6 : 0.4$ and higher. In electrolyte (b), the copper content increased from 75 to 87% at $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Ni}^{2+} = 0.6 : 0.4$ and did not change by increasing this ratio (Fig. 4). The constant content of copper in the alloy at this ratio and higher is related to the depolarization effect of the alloy formation on nickel deposition. At this ratio and at higher ratios, the more positive the deposition potential of the alloy, the higher the degree of depolarization of nickel deposition. Thus the rate of deposition of both copper and nickel will be constant.

Fig. 4

The effect of current density :

Contrary to the pyrophosphate electrolytes, in which the alloy composition goes through a minimum relative to copper content on increasing the current density^{4,5}, in the citrate bath no minimum was noticed at all. The copper content always decreased by increasing the current density in both electrolytes (Fig. 5). This is explained by the fact that the

Fig. 5

cathodic polarization of copper deposition is not higher than that of nickel. On increasing the current density, the deposition potential of the alloy shifts to more negative values close to those of nickel deposition, specially over the limiting current on the polarization curves (Fig. 3).

In electrolyte, (a), the copper content decreases gradually from 96.5% at 0.25 a/dm² to 93.0% at 1.0 a/dm². On further increasing of current density, the copper content decreases suddenly to 77% at 2.0 a/dm². In the presence of 1.0N NH_4OH (electrolyte b), the sudden decrease in copper content starts almost from the beginning. At 0.5 a/dm² and higher, the change in the alloy composition becomes very smooth by increasing the current density. The values of current densities at which the sudden change in the alloy composition takes place correspond to the limiting current of copper deposition on the polarization curves.

The effect of temperature and stirring :

Increasing the temperature from 30° to 60° resulted in increasing the nickel content in the alloy (Fig. 5). This is explained by the fact that temperature affects the cathodic polarization of nickel much more than that of copper. Because of this, deposition potentials of copper and nickel become closer and nickel content rises in the alloy.

The mechanical stirring of the electrolytes during the deposition enriches the alloy with copper. This is explained by the fact that the cathodic polarization of copper deposition is almost of diffusional nature, while that of nickel is of chemical type, i.e., stirring will make the Cu^{2+} discharge much easier than Ni^{2+} discharge.

Both stirring and heating made the deposit of lower quality. The deposit turns darker and its grains become coarser.

The current efficiency and quality of the deposit :

The current efficiency of the cathodic deposition of Cu-Ni alloy from citrate electrolytes is close to the theoretical one. In the presence of ammonium hydroxide (electrolyte b), the current efficiency is always lower than in its absence. The higher the ammonium hydroxide concentration, the lower the current efficiency (90-95%). In the absence of ammonium hydroxide (electrolyte a), the current efficiency amounts to 98%. Stirring and heating of the electrolytes increased the current efficiency.

The deposit has many pittings in the absence of H_3BO_3 , while in its presence no pittings were noticed. The quality of the Cu-Ni alloy is always better in the presence of ammonium hydroxide than in its absence. The alloy deposited at current densities 0.5-1.5 a/dm² is of the best quality.

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